

The contribution of Data-driven poverty alleviation funds in achieving Mid-21st-Century Multidimensional Poverty Alleviation Planning

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Abstract: The first Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) is intended to eradicate multi-dimensional poverty globally. The same multidimensional poverty indices for India and the Middle East/Africa in 2020 indicate that 10-14 years are still required to reach the level of China's poverty eradication. Using machine learning, spatial statistics, and a scenario analysis, we demonstrate how a Monte Carlo simulation of poverty alleviation funds-guided shared socioeconomic pathways (PAFs-SSPs) in China reveals the necessity to adopt an integrated poverty alleviation strategy. This approach employs multi-dimensional development indicators to reduce wide regional differences. We developed the data-driven model framework of a PAFs-SSPs to analyze the multifaceted and long-term planning needs of poverty alleviation policies, which can be applied to the formulation of poverty alleviation policies in different developing countries. Our findings point to the importance of implementing multidimensional development policies in China to achieve the first SDG worldwide.

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Supplementary files

Table SI. Multidimensional poverty (MP) in previous studies and related research methods

Scale	Problem	Method	Ref.
Global	Measurement of severe poverty	Alkire–Foster	1
	Intertemporal change of MP	Alkire–Foster	2
	MP and financial factors	Fuzzy measures	3
	The evolution of national poverty	Alkire and Foster	4
Country	Income poverty	Alkire and Foster	5
	Socio-economic outcomes affect poverty	Regression	6
Province	MP of children and its dynamic changes	Alkire–Foster	7
	Measuring poverty and inequality	Combined methodology	8
	Incidence of MP	Alkire–Foster	9
City/county	Regional differences at county scale	RMDI	10
	Identifying and measuring poor counties	CDI	11
Township	Measuring and identifying poor areas	DFID	12
	MP Measurement Standard	Hybrid Bayesian	13
	Analysis influencing factors of rural poverty	Spatial regression	14

The related factor of MPI on a global scale is presented in Table SII. As we are all well aware, the economy is growing and resources are shrinking. In comparison to the aforementioned indices, the growth tendency of welfare and regression tendency of the environment is not synonymous, and many volatilities are apparent. Considering the imbalance of poverty alleviation in different regions and the importance of achieving collaborative development in different aspects of poverty, the UN SDGs propose to promote multidimensional poverty alleviation. Multidimensional poverty areas (MPAs) are mainly concentrated in sub-Saharan Africa (proportions for economic, resource, welfare, and environmental poverty respectively are 39.51%, 36.36%, 30.77%, 32.26%) and Asia (41.97%, 63.63%, 30.7%, 34.4%).

Table SII. Multiple factors of MPI on a global scale

Dimension	Ordinal	Index
Environmental (X1)	1	CO2 emissions (KT)
	2	Proportion of forest area (%)
Resource (X2)	1	Land resources per capita (HA)
	2	Production index of animal husbandry
Economic (X3)	1	Per capita GDP
	2	Agricultural value added as a percentage of GDP

	3	Industrial added value as a percentage of GDP
	4	Average night light intensity
Welfare (X4)	1	Hospital beds (per 1,000 people)
	2	Enrolment, secondary education (percentage of total population)

Table SIII. The intersection points of MPI under different SSPs between China and the USA

China \ USA	SSP1-2.6	SSP2-4.5	SSP3-7.0	SSP4-3.4	SSP5-3.4
SSP1-2.6	2095(1.36)	2065(0.841)	2060(0.785)	---	--
SSP2-4.5	---	---	---	---	---
SSP3-7.0	---	---	---	---	---
SSP4-3.4	---	2095(1.03)	2090(0.957)	---	---
SSP5-3.4	2065(1.04)	2050(0.746)	2050(0.727)	2070(1.13)	2075(1.23)

Table SIV. Data sources and descriptions of MPI

1st indices	2nd indices	Data Source
Environmental	Altitude	MODIS
	Average slope	MODIS
	Vegetation coverage	MODIS
	Vegetation normalization index	MODIS
	Biological land quality	MODIS
Resources	Per capita land resource ownership	Statistical yearbook
	Total output value of per capita agriculture, forestry, animal husbandry, and fishery	Statistical yearbook
Economic	Total GDP (100 million yuan)	Statistical yearbook
	GDP per capita (yuan/person)	Statistical yearbook
	Total retail sales of social consumer goods per capita	Statistical yearbook
	Average night light intensity	DMSP/OLS, NPP/VIIRS
	Per capita disposable income of rural residents	Statistical yearbook
Social	Number of beds in hospitals and health centers per 10,000	Statistical yearbook
	Number of middle school students per 10,000	Statistical yearbook

Figure 1. The identification accuracy of poverty-stricken counties in different provinces and regions of China. The identification results of poverty alleviation counties in Beijing, Fujian, Guangdong, Hunan, Jiangsu, Liaoning, Qinghai, Shandong, Shanghai, Zhejiang, Tianjin, Tibet, Taiwan, Hong Kong, and Macao are 100%, and those for Henan, Xinjiang, and Jilin provinces are less than 60%. Henan, as a populous province in China, has a higher MPI value due to its large nighttime light data index caused by its massive population. Xinjiang has a brighter spot due to its vast land area, which leads to a large margin of error.

Figure S2. The nonlinear relationship between PAFs and MPI in Anhui province. Counties in the province can be divided into poor counties and non-poor counties. Each builds a model to learn the relevant parameters.

Figure S3. The MPI distribution in different years in China. The MPI gap in China gradually narrowed and the development approach tended to be collaborative, indicated by the number of poverty counties decreasing. Distribution centers of mean MPI in China's counties are gradually increasing, which indicates that the depth of poverty is gradually reducing and the economic development of counties is steadily improving.

Table SV. The MPI Distribution of counties in China from 2012-2017

Year	Mean of MPI	Std of MPI
2012	3.087	1.839
2013	3.460	1.902
2014	4.102	2.061
2015	4.291	2.095
2016	4.367	2.111
2017	4.941	2.215

Figure S4. Analysis of the poverty depth of poverty alleviation counties in China from the “vertical-horizontal” dimension. (a) Tendency of the number of poverty alleviation counties in poverty-stricken areas; (b) Tendency of the changing rate of poverty alleviation counties in poor areas; (c) The changing rate of number of poverty alleviation counties in poor areas; (d) The relationship between investment in national poverty alleviation funds and the number of poverty alleviation counties. From the left to the right of the x-axis in (a), changes in the MPI poverty boundary increase gradually with the number of national poverty alleviation counties. From the top to the bottom of the y-axis, the number of poverty-stricken counties is decreasing year by year. The tendency characteristics of the number of poverty alleviation counties has shifted to the right with the continuous investment in national poverty alleviation funds. To further explore the evolution tendency of the number of poverty-stricken counties, sliding filtering of the first-order difference of the number of poverty-stricken counties with different MPI values was conducted in (b). (c) shows the second-order difference of the changing rate of the number of poverty alleviation counties with the MPI after sliding filtering. (b) shows that the change rate of the number of poverty alleviation counties is first decreasing and then increasing (from left to right), and the inflection point of the MPI transformation is also increasing. Furthermore, the number of poverty-stricken counties is decreasing year by year due to the government’s investment in poverty alleviation, as illustrated in (d). With the continuous investment in national poverty alleviation funds and the proposal of targeted poverty alleviation policies, poverty alleviation areas have been developed rapidly, and the number of poverty alleviation counties has rapidly reduced.

(a) **(b)**

Figure S5. Spatial distribution of MPI in counties in China. (a) Multidimensional poverty properties of China in 2012; (b) Multidimensional poverty properties of China in 2017. Poverty identification by a single factor is unable to comprehensively and accurately reveal the overall level of poverty. Most poverty-stricken counties have been lifted out of economic poverty. However, gaps remain in environmental poverty, social welfare, and other factors.

Figure S6. The accuracy of the regression method evaluated by root-mean-square error (RMSE) and sum of squares for error (SSE). (a) The RMSE in the various regression methods; (b) The SSE in the various regression methods. 500 repetition tests were used for statistical analysis. Machine-learning methods included support-vector machine,¹⁵ logistic regression,¹⁶ *k*-nearest neighbor,¹⁷ decision tree based on the Gaussian function,¹⁸ neural networks,¹⁹ decision tree ensemble learning,²⁰ and random forest.²¹

Table SVI. Multidimensional analysis of nonlinear fitting accuracy between MPI and NLS

Year	Methods	RMSE	SSE
2012	Linear regression	0.5217 ± 0.1501	18.496 ± 5.53
	Polynomial fitting	0.5381 ± 0.1464	18.247 ± 5.44
	Cubic function fitting	0.5198 ± 0.1508	19.151 ± 5.18
	Quartic function fitting	0.5128 ± 0.1537	18.565 ± 5.31
	NN	0.6015 ± 0.1861	21.407 ± 6.61
	SVM	0.5386 ± 0.1614	19.167 ± 5.72
	Decision tree	0.3735 ± 0.1278	13.29 ± 4.52
	Random forest	0.2264 ± 0.0678	8.058 ± 2.39

Figure S7. Spatial distribution of MPI in SSP2 scenarios. This image shows the spatial evolution property of SSP2 pathways in 2012, 2025, 2035 and 2050, respectively. The MPI poverty mainly in three regions in terms of Henan-Shandong, Guangdong-Hainan, Yunan-Guangxi in 2025. The primary development mainly in Yunan and at 2035.

Figure S8. Spatial distribution of MPI in SSP3 scenarios. This image shows the spatial evolution property of SSP3 pathways in 2012, 2025, 2035 and 2050, respectively. The MPI poverty mainly in three regions in terms of Shandong, Guangdong-Hainan, Yunan in 2025. The primary development mainly in Yunan and at 2035.

Figure S9. Spatial distribution of MPI in SSP4 scenarios. This image shows the spatial evolution property of SSP4 pathways in 2012, 2025, 2035 and 2050, respectively. The MPI poverty mainly in three regions in terms of Guangdong-Hainan, Yunan in 2025. The primary development mainly in Yunan and at 2035.

Figure S10. Spatial distribution of MPI in SSP5 scenarios. This image shows the spatial evolution property of SSP5 pathways in 2012, 2025, 2035 and 2050, respectively. The MPI poverty mainly in three regions in terms of Guangdong-Hainan, Yunan in 2025. The primary development mainly in Yunan and at 2035.

References

1. Alkire, S. & Santos, M. E. Measuring Acute Poverty in the Developing World: Robustness and Scope of the Multidimensional Poverty Index. *World Dev.* 59, 251–274 (2014).
2. Alkire, S., Roche, J. M. & Vaz, A. Changes Over Time in Multidimensional Poverty: Methodology and Results for 34 Countries. *World Dev.* **94**, 232–249 (2017).
3. Ciani, M., Gagliardi, F., Riccarelli, S. & Betti, G. Fuzzy measures of multidimensional poverty in the Mediterranean area: A focus on financial dimension. *Sustain.* **11**, (2019).
4. Berenger, V. The counting approach to multidimensional poverty. The case of four African countries. *South African J. Econ.* **87**, 200–227 (2019).
5. Alkire, S. & Fang, Y. Dynamics of Multidimensional Poverty and Uni-dimensional Income

- Poverty: An Evidence of Stability Analysis from China. *Soc. Indic. Res.* **142**, 25–64 (2019).
6. Loayza, N. & Rigolini, J. The Local Impact of Mining on Poverty and Inequality: Evidence from the Commodity Boom in Peru. *World Dev.* **84**, 219–234 (2016).
 7. Qi, D. & Wu, Y. A multidimensional child poverty index in China. *Child. Youth Serv. Rev.* **57**, 159–170 (2015).
 8. Noel, M. & Alperin, P. Groupe de Recherche en Économie et Développement International Cahier de recherche / Working Paper Inequalities in Poverty : Evidence from Argentina. (2006).
 9. Khan, A. U., Saboor, A., Hussain, A., Sadiq, S. & Mohsin, A. Q. Investigating Multidimensional Poverty across the Regions in the Sindh Province of Pakistan. *Soc. Indic. Res.* **119**, 515–532 (2014).
 10. Xu, Y., Duan, J. & Xu, X. Comprehensive methods for measuring regional multidimensional development and their applications in China. *J. Geogr. Sci.* **28**, 1182–1196 (2018).
 11. Yuanzhi, G., Yang, Z. & Zhi, C. Geographical patterns and anti-poverty targeting post-2020 in China. *J. Geogr. Sci.* **28**, 1810–1824 (2018).
 12. Liu, Y. & Xu, Y. A geographic identification of multidimensional poverty in rural China under the framework of sustainable livelihoods analysis. *Appl. Geogr.* **73**, 62–76 (2016).
 13. Nájera Catalán, H. E., Fifita, V. K. & Faingaanuku, W. Small-Area Multidimensional Poverty Estimates for Tonga 2016: Drawn from a Hierarchical Bayesian Estimator. *Appl. Spat. Anal. Policy* **13**, 305–328 (2020).
 14. Zhang, J. *et al.* Analyzing Influencing Factors of Rural Poverty in Typical Poverty Areas of Hainan Province: A Case Study of Lingao County. *Chinese Geogr. Sci.* **28**, 1061–1076 (2018).
 15. Amari, S. & Wu, S. Improving support vector machine classifiers by modifying kernel functions. **12**, 783–789 (1999).
 16. Yang, Y. & Loog, M. A benchmark and comparison of active learning for logistic regression. *Pattern Recognit.* **83**, 401–415 (2018).
 17. Yu, Z. *et al.* Hybrid k -Nearest Neighbor Classifier. **46**, 1263–1275 (2016).
 18. Member, A. Kernel-Based Feature Extraction with a Speech. **52**, 2250–2263 (2004).
 19. Hecht-nielsen, R. the Backpropagation Neural Network. 593–605.
 20. Agrawal, R. K., Muchahary, F. & Tripathi, M. M. Ensemble of relevance vector machines and boosted trees for electricity price forecasting. *Appl. Energy* **250**, 540–548 (2019).
 21. Aldersley, A., Murray, S. J. & Cornell, S. E. Global and regional analysis of climate and human drivers of wildfire. *Sci. Total Environ.* **409**, 3472–3481 (2011).
 22. Liu, Y. & Xu, Y. A geographic identification of multidimensional poverty in rural China under the framework of sustainable livelihoods analysis. *Appl. Geogr.* **73**, 62–76 (2016).